

Chemical constituents of the stems of *Acacia arabica* (Lamk.)

Bimla, Meera, Rajvir Singh and S. B. Kalidhar*

Department of Chemistry, CCS Haryana Agricultural University, Hisar-125 004, India

E-mail : kalidhar@hau.nic.in Fax : 91-1662-234613

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Acacidiol, resorcinol, methyl gallate, methyl 5-*O*-methylgallate and ecosanamide have been isolated from the stems of *Acacia arabica*. Of these, methyl 5-*O*-methylgallate is a hitherto unreported compound.

Acacia arabica (Lamk.), synonymous with *Acacia nilotica* L., belongs¹ to the family Leguminosae and the subfamily Mimosaceae. The plant is known² to cure cough, bronchitis, diarrhoea, dysentery, piles and urinary discharges. The main constituents³ of the plant (bark, heartwood, flowers, pods, roots and leaves) are known to have skeletons of gallic acid, flavone and catechin. As there is no report on the chemical constituents of its stems, the present study was undertaken.

Stems of *A. arabica* (4 kg), obtained from Landscape, H.A.U., Hisar, were chopped into small pieces and air-dried. The extraction was carried out with hot methanol. Extractives were subjected to silica gel column chromatography. Five compounds (A1-A5) were isolated with the eluates (i) benzene, (ii) ethyl acetate-benzene (1 : 19), (iii) ethyl acetate-benzene (1 : 19), (iv) ethyl acetate-benzene (1 : 9), (v) ethyl acetate-benzene (1 : 4), (vi) ethyl acetate-benzene (1 : 3) respectively. Spectra were recorded on Bruker AC 300 F 300 MHz NMR spectrometer in CDCl₃ using TMS as the internal standard, Hitachi 570 IR spectrophotometer and VG 705 11-250J GCMS-DS spectrophotometer. A comparison of spectral and other data of A1, A2, A4 and A5 with the literature confirmed these four compounds to be acacidiol⁴, resorcinol⁵, methyl gallate⁶ and ecosanamide⁶ respectively.

The compound A3 gave green colour with alcoholic FeCl₃ indicating its phenolic nature. The IR spectrum showed the presence of carbonyl (1694 cm⁻¹) and hydroxyl groups (3319 and 3467 cm⁻¹). The ¹H NMR of the compound showed two singlets at δ 7.20 and 7.17, each for one proton, indicating the presence of two aromatic protons in the compound. Two singlets at δ 5.55 and 5.24, each for one proton, could be due to two hydroxyls on the aromatic ring. A singlet at δ 3.86, for three protons, was assignable to -COOMe protons. The data suggested the compound A3 to be methyl 5-methoxy gal-

- 1 R₁ = R₂ = H, R₃ = Me
- 2 R₁ = R₂ = R₃ = Me
- 3 R₁ = R₃ = H, R₂ = Me

late (1). The elemental analysis also supported the proposed structure.

Dimethyl derivative of the compound A3 has been found to be identical with methyl tri-*O*-methylgallate (2) confirming the present isolate to be methyl 5-*O*-methylgallate. The alternative structure methyl 4-*O*-methylgallate (3) is ruled out by the fact that H-2 and H-6 are observed at different δ values. In 3, H-2 and H-6 should appear as one singlet because these are identical protons in 3. This is the first report of the isolation and characterisation of 1.

Methyl 5-*O*-methylgallate (1) : It crystallised from methanol as a light yellow solid, 30 mg, m.p. 151°. It gave green colour with alcoholic FeCl₃ (Found : C, 54.53; H, 5.04. C₉H₁₀O₅ required : C, 54.54; H, 5.05%); ν_{max} (nujol) 553, 768, 1003, 1037, 1196, 1252, 1315, 1442, 1619, 1694, 1954, 3084, 3319, 3467; ¹H NMR (δ, CDCl₃) 7.20 (1H, s, H-2), 7.17 (1H, s, H-6), 5.55 (1H, s, OH-3), 5.24 (1H, s, OH-4), 3.86 (3H, s, COOCH₃), 3.70 (3H, s, OCH₃). Methylation, K₂CO₃/Me₂SO₄, m.p. 82° (lit. m.p. 82.5°).

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Note

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